

PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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Annotation: Learning a foreign language is directly related to the student immersion in the culture of its people. In modern conditions a foreign language is seen as a means of communication and as a means of attracting students to the culture of a people. It is gradually becoming the dominant strategy of foreign language teaching in education and causes the necessity in formation of students' professional competence of foreign language.

Key Terms: competence, Professional competence, Methodological competence, pedagogical competence, creative competence, autonomous competence, socio-cultural competence, linguistic (lexical, grammatical, and phonetic), communicative (speaking, listening, reading, writing), linguocultural competence; subjective (informative-thematic, conceptual) and methodological competence.

INTRODUCTION

In the methodology of professional training in foreign languages, professional competence is understood as an ability based on professional knowledge and skills, educational and life experience, values and individual inclinations, allowing to effectively solve communicatively-teaching tasks arising in real situations of professional pedagogical activity.

Foreign language teacher profession's competence was developed by S. F. Shatilov, K. I. Salomatov and E. S. Rabunsky, interprets the professional competence of a teacher foreign language as follows. Since the main purpose of teaching a foreign language in education is the mastery of students of a foreign

language as a new way of communicating communicatively level, then, according to the compilers of the profession's frame, the communicative and educational function of pedagogical activity a foreign language teacher is the leading, fundamental, it largely determines the content of all other functions. The above functions in the professional activities of a foreign language teacher can be divided into two groups: to the group of goal-setting functions (communicative-educational, developing, educating) and the group of operational-structural functions: Gnostic, constructive-planning, organizational.

BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE

Today, there are various options for the structure of professional competence of a foreign teacher language. As an example, one can imagine a variant developed by V.V. Safonova, according to which the structure of the competency of a foreign language teacher includes following components: communicative, language, speech, regional geography, cultural studies, linguodidactic, subject competence.

According to Yu. V. Eremin, the special language training of a foreign language teacher at a secondary school at a pedagogical university includes the following interrelated components: practical language training (communicative competence); general philological (literary, regional and linguistic and regional) training = theoretical and linguistic competence); methodological training (linguistic and methodological competence); professional and communicative training (didactic-communicative competence).

In accordance with the concept of Yu. V. Eremin, the basis of didactic-communicative competence, which is the condition of the executive phase of professional and pedagogical activity of a foreign language teacher is knowledge and skills that form the communicative, theoretical and linguistic and linguistic and competence of a professional teacher. In didactic-communicative competence teachers, as in focus, concentrates everything that is necessary teacher to

successfully carry out communicative and educational activities in the lesson.

N.V. Bagramova, M.K. Kolkova, I.P. Shishkin offer own scheme of the professional competence of a foreign language teacher. According to the scheme, the basis of professional competence teachers of a foreign language compose linguistic and speech competencies.

Language competence is knowledge and erudition in a foreign language, possession of the rules of analysis and synthesis of units that allow you to build sentences; This is the possession of a system of information about the language being studied by its levels: phonetics, vocabulary, composition of words and word formation, morphology, simple syntax and complex sentences, the basics of the style of the text. On quality language competence in the studied language is affected not only by the degree of proficiency in it, but also by the level of competence of students in their native language. According to Chomsky, linguistic competence means the ability to understand and produce an unlimited number of linguistically correct sentences with the help of learned linguistic signs and rules for their connection (Azimov E. G., Schukin A. N. 1999).

Speech competence is the ability to use a foreign language for the purposes of personal and professional foreign language communication, adapt the language in order to teach schoolchildren the basics of foreign language communication; it is the possession of the ways of forming and formulating thoughts through language and skill use such methods in the process of perception and generation of speech.

METHODOLOGY

Intellectual readiness to solve problems of mastering a foreign language as a means of communication involves the presence of linguistic, communicative and technical (operational rational) competence, that is, knowledge of linguistic material, possession of methods, techniques and means of actualization of this knowledge in a specific situation, possession of skills reading, listening, speaking

and writing in the target language.

The teacher must have a broad general philological base, which is necessary for him in his daily professional activities teachers of a foreign language. It's about knowledge of literature, history, country studies, linguistic studies, art and other branches of general philological training of teachers, whom he so often lacks.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

Based on the professional competency scheme of a foreign language teacher proposed by A.F. Kononova, we in turn, we single out a number of skills within the framework of basic and special competencies. So, to general professional skills (basic competencies) foreign language teachers include: taking into account the level of formation of key competencies (level of training and culture) of students; taking into account the psychological characteristics of the personality of the student; organizational skills; planning of lessons and independent work of students; mastery of a teacher's didactic speech; taking into account sociocultural interference and positive transfer; the ability to notice and correct errors; control of student knowledge; work with technical training tools; the use of special literature in their professional pedagogical activities. To special professional skills (special competencies) include methodical skills (in which we also include acting (playing) skills) and communicative skills, which are based on theoretical and practical (linguistic, speech) knowledge and skills, and also competence in the socio-cultural sphere, interactive competence, educational and cognitive and compensatory skills(Kononova A, 2004). All these skills are closely interconnected and complement each other, and together indicate the professional competence of a foreign language teacher.

Within the framework (Figure 3) of basic competencies are distinguished (Kononova A.2005): - psychological and pedagogical competence of the teacher allows to shape the personality of students, conduct moral, aesthetic, patriotic and

socio-cultural education in educational process and extracurricular activities using foreign language means taking into account regional geographic and socio-cultural information, form the motivational sphere of students, interest in learning a foreign language;

- intercultural competence, ensuring the implementation of the dialogue of cultures in the process of teaching a foreign language as a means of intercultural communication, familiarization with culture countries of the language studied;
- reflective competence, including the ability to analyze one's own activity and correct it, to critically approach oneself.

Professional competencies consist of methodological and communicative competencies.

Methodological competence provides organization and managing the process of mastering a foreign language. The main functions of a teacher of a foreign language and determine teacher's methodological competence: communicative-educational, constructive-planning, organizational, controlling, gnostic function. Regarding the process of teaching language, the leading goal-setting function is communicative and educational. The set of methodological knowledge and skills required to solve the set methodological problems, is the methodological competence of the teacher, determining his ability to the successful implementation of their professional activities. The methodological competence, in accordance with the set goal, determines the choice of certain methodological technologies required by the teacher to successfully solve the before him is a methodological task.

Communicative competence is to implement communicative-activity approach that guides English classes for teaching communication, for using the language to exchange thoughts. The components of communicative competence include: linguistic competence covering linguistic and speech competencies;

compensatory competence, including the ability to compensate for the lack of knowledge, skills in the process communication; interactive competency, implying skill communicate, interact with communication partners; educational and cognitive competency, covering two aspect:

a) creative competence, which manifests itself in a creative approach to teaching and learning a foreign language, in an original approach to the selection and presentation of educational material, the use of non-standard forms of work, constant professional self-improvement;

b) autonomous competence, i.e. a large amount of independent work in the process of professional development "Ability to learn";

c) sociocultural competence, with its components linguistic and cultural and cultural and regional studies competencies.

Linguistic and regional competence involves ability to work with text, ability to extract from units language cultural and regional geographic information and use it, achieving full communication. Teacher's cultural and regional competence includes knowledge of the country of the language being studied (knowledge of geography, history, national customs, traditions, realities) providing adequate communication using national cultural language component. All these competencies are closely interconnected, complement each other.

According to European standard, 5 basic competences provide adaptation, self-realization in the market conditions(Blomeke S. & Delaney S,2012):

1. Social-political competence or readiness to problem-solving;
2. Information competence;
3. Communicative competence;
4. Social and socio-cultural competence (in the model of communicative competence includes itself socio-cultural competence as one of the components)
5. Readiness to long-life learning.

The social-political competence related to the readiness to problem-solving and be responsible for decision-making. People face different problems in their life and psychological readiness to react to problems is topical, so teachers should train them to solve problems and be responsible for their actions. Teachers can develop reflective skills related to a certain situation, social roles, communicants' intentions and feelings to solve academic and life activities. For example, students should solve basic academic tasks as compensate the omitted material; to get needed consultations; prepare successfully to the testing; choose the educational course or educational establishment; define the appropriate form of education; formulate the topic and define possible forms of presentation of project or research work; prepare a report in the oral or written form for a conference; compile the bibliography, award a scientific grant or practical study; organize a seminar, a round-table discussion, a council.

The core of the information competence can be interpreted as a set of readiness and needs to work with all types of modern media and academic resources in professional and everyday life spheres of individuals' activity. Nowadays the information competence¹ literacy is often replaced with the media literacy as ability to interact with the media information adequately in the global information space, especially, to search the necessary information, to analyze and evaluate it critically, to create media-texts, which are extended by different media means of mass information and communication in various forms.

The communicative competence of the FL specialists is related to professional literacy which includes the following components: 1) linguistic (lexical, grammatical, and phonetic); 2) communicative (speaking, listening, reading, writing); 3) linguocultural; 4) social-cultural; 5) subjective (informative-thematic,

¹ in the sphere of education, a special attention is paid to forming or development information-communication competence, also called as e-competence

conceptual) and 6) methodological.

Readiness to long-life learning correlates with the continuous education, which the Uzbek model of education demonstrates it. As we see, reforms have an affect on the curriculum, teaching materials and assessment – all of which are crucial in the preparation of skilful modern languages teachers and in which they must be trained and retrained (See *Figure 1*).

Figure 1. Reformation components of education

The best teachers possess a range of educational proficiencies. Teachers are expected to be competent in several key areas to be considered effective teachers. According to the National Board for Professional Teaching Standards, teachers are expected to demonstrate competency in five core areas. These five competencies are the basis by which teacher's effectiveness typically is measured (Jalolov J.J. Makhkamova G.T., Ashurov Sh.S.,2015).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

As we see professional communicative competence has in itself social and socio-cultural, and other ones. Optimization of the process of foreign language teaching involves the development of certain areas of instructional activity,

interactive teaching methods, cooperation between a teacher and students, modern equipment and facilities in classes, learner-centred teaching, information-communication technologies and assessment tools². Thus communicative competence (proficiency) is a result of modern language teaching, the components of which are enshrined in the CEFR's six reference levels (A1, A2, B1, B2, C1, C2)³. In the scientific literature on methodology various models of communicative competence (Celce-Murcia 2007:41–57) have been suggested. In current interpretation, communicative competence includes the ability to display linguistic, sociolinguistic, discourse, and strategic, socio-cultural and social competences (Van Ek 1986). The local model contains linguistic, sociolinguistic and pragmatic competences.

Linguistic (language) competence presupposes acquiring knowledge about the language system, rules of language items functioning in the speech and ability to comprehend and produce speech.

Sociolinguistic competence is also called as speech competence in the local methodology as well as by that we understand knowledge about ways or strategies of forming and formulating ideas with the help of language providing opportunities to organize, comprehend and undertake speech action for implementation of communicative intention, as well as ability to understand and express ideas via these ways.

Pragmatic competence was considered as part of sociolinguistic competence, which is described as ability to comprehend and produce speech acts or speech acts set. According to Cenoz (2007: 125-126), pragmatic competence envelops socio-pragmatic and linguo-pragmatic aspects of speech acts.

² Using CEFR: Principles of Good Practice. – Cambridge: CUP, 2011

³ Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning. Teaching. The Council of Europe. – Strasbourg, 2001

In addition, it involves the knowledge of cultural aspects such as the rules of behaviour that exist in the target language community, as well as cross-cultural specifics, including differences and similarities in intercultural communication.

Thus socio-cultural competence is an ability to communicate in a language appropriately, situationally and culturally. It is the knowledge of customs, rules, beliefs and principles of a given society.

In short, professional competence for a teacher means perfection and the embodiment of all potential. A teacher not only teaches, but also sets an example for students.

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